

EFFECTIVE APPROACHES TO STATISTICAL DATA ACCOUNTING IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY

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Abstract

In the context of the digital economy, transitioning to modern technologies in statistical accounting has become essential for enhancing data accuracy, timeliness, and processing efficiency. This study analyzes key issues within traditional accounting methods and proposes digital approaches, such as automation, cloud technologies, and artificial intelligence, to address these challenges. The recommendations outlined in this research focus on investments in digital infrastructure, specialist training, and systemic data integration, aiming to modernize

statistical accounting and equip organizations with high-quality data for decision-making. Future research perspectives include the development of flexible data integration systems and an exploration of AI's role in ensuring long-term accounting accuracy.

Keywords: *Digital economy, statistical accounting, automation, cloud technologies, artificial intelligence, data integration, data quality, digital transformation*

Introduction

With the rapid development of the digital economy, the collection and accounting of statistical data have become increasingly critical in supporting strategic planning and management decisions. Each year, the volume of real-time data grows, opening new horizons for economic analysis and forecasting. However, to effectively utilize this data, reliable and modern methods of statistical accounting are essential, which underscores the relevance of this research. The article "Methodological Aspects of the Digital Economy in the Focus of Statistical Forecasting Methods" highlights that traditional accounting methods require substantial adaptation to meet the accuracy and efficiency demands of the digital economy [1]. These changes are necessary for organizations to make well-informed decisions, establishing the importance of this research.

The aim of this study is to identify and analyze approaches that can ensure effective statistical data accounting in the context of digital economic transformation. To achieve this goal, the following objectives have been set:

1. Analyze existing approaches to statistical data accounting and their applicability in the digital environment.
2. Identify the main issues related to data processing, integration, and verification.
3. Determine technologies and methods that improve the accuracy, responsiveness, and efficiency of statistical accounting.

Several significant barriers emerge in the digital transformation of statistical accounting. First, as noted in "Defining the Digital Economy for Statistical Research Purposes," the challenge of integrating data from various sources complicates standardization and increases the risk of accounting errors [2]. With the rising volume and diversity of data, the unification of information streams becomes increasingly complex. Second, the reliability of digital data is often questioned due to its dynamic nature and multiple sources, necessitating rigorous verification. Finally, manual processing of large volumes of information becomes ineffective, prompting many experts to advocate for automating accounting processes [3]. These issues complicate the use of statistical data in managerial decision-making, emphasizing the need to explore approaches capable of addressing these challenges.

Based on the above, the hypothesis is that the adoption of modern technologies—such as cloud computing, artificial intelligence, and big data analytics—can significantly enhance the accuracy and efficiency of statistical accounting in the digital economy. As demonstrated in the Digital Economy and Society Index (DESI), countries actively implementing digital technologies in data accounting and management achieve higher efficiency in data collection and processing [4]. Therefore, this study hypothesizes that the automation of accounting processes, grounded in advanced technologies, can effectively address existing issues and ensure the data accuracy required for sound management decisions.

Methods

In this study, a comprehensive analysis of recent publications and scholarly articles addressing the challenges and approaches to statistical accounting within the digital economy was conducted. A review of the current literature revealed two main directions in approaches to statistical accounting: traditional methods and modern digital technologies, such as automation, cloud solutions, and artificial intelligence algorithms. The article "*Methodological Aspects of the Digital Economy with a Focus on Statistical Forecasting Methods*" [1] highlights that traditional accounting methods often prove ineffective given the continuously increasing data volumes, which necessitates their revision and improvement. At the same time, as emphasized in the article "*Defining the Digital Economy for Statistical Research Purposes*" [2], digital technologies, despite their advantages in speed and flexibility, encounter challenges in data integration and accuracy assurance. Therefore, the literature review enabled the identification of key advantages and limitations of various approaches, forming a foundation for further analysis.

Both qualitative and quantitative analysis methods were employed to achieve the research objectives. Within the qualitative analysis, case studies from scholarly publications and official reports were examined, featuring examples of implementing digital technologies in statistical accounting. The quantitative analysis involved the processing of statistical data from open sources, such as the Digital Economy and Society Index (DESI) database [4] and national statistical reports. These methods enabled an assessment of the effectiveness and challenges of both traditional and contemporary statistical accounting methods.

The study employed digital tools and technologies that have proven effective in practical applications of statistical accounting. Notably, cloud solutions like Amazon Web Services and Google Cloud facilitate the storage and processing of large volumes of data, improving their accessibility and usability. Artificial intelligence and machine learning methods are actively used to automate data processing and analysis, enhancing processing speed and accuracy. Furthermore, big

data technologies enable the integration of information from diverse sources, providing a comprehensive approach to statistical accounting [3].

Data collection for this study was conducted using a variety of sources. Key sources included publications in academic journals and articles available on CyberLeninka, which provide current research on the digital economy [1, 2]. Statistical data were obtained from open sources such as DESI [4] and official statistical reports, which offer insights into the level of digitalization in various countries and regions. These data sources formed the foundation for analyzing existing issues and identifying opportunities for improving statistical accounting within the digital economy.

Results

The findings of this study confirm that traditional statistical accounting methods face significant limitations in the context of a digital economy. One of the primary issues is their inability to efficiently process large volumes of data—a particularly critical problem in the era of digitalization, where information flows from multiple sources in various formats. As emphasized in the article “Methodological Aspects of the Digital Economy in the Focus of Statistical Forecasting Methods,” traditional accounting approaches hinder the timely and accurate retrieval of data, as many processes remain reliant on manual intervention, increasing the risk of delays and errors [1]. These limitations also include challenges in integrating data from diverse sources, particularly when multi-system approaches complicate data standardization and unification [2].

This study analyzed successful digital accounting methods, including the automation of data collection and processing, the use of cloud technologies, and artificial intelligence (AI) techniques. The results indicate that automation significantly accelerates accounting processes and reduces error rates by minimizing human involvement. The use of cloud technologies, as illustrated in the Digital Economy and Society Index (DESI), facilitates data unification and simplifies integration, which is critical for organizations handling large amounts of information [4]. AI and machine learning provide additional capabilities for analysis and forecasting, allowing for the identification of patterns and trends in data that may have previously gone unnoticed [3].

An analysis of the data reveals significant improvements in the quality of statistical accounting when modern approaches are used. The application of cloud technologies enhances data accessibility and flexibility, positively impacting processing speed. For example, DESI shows that countries actively employing cloud services and AI achieve higher levels of information processing speed [4]. AI also enhances data accuracy through automated verification and analysis, which can greatly reduce discrepancies. In the study “Statistical Assessment of Digitalization

Levels in Russia: Challenges and Prospects,” it is demonstrated that the use of big data and automation enables the consolidation of fragmented information streams, facilitating access to analytical data and improving data integration across systems [2]. Ultimately, digital approaches provide a higher level of operational efficiency and accounting accuracy, a vital factor given the dynamic nature of the digital economy.

Discussion

The results indicate that the integration of digital technologies into statistical accounting has a positive impact on the efficiency and accuracy of data management. Contemporary approaches, such as automation, cloud-based solutions, and artificial intelligence techniques, reduce data processing time, improve accessibility, and enhance precision by minimizing human errors. These technologies help address traditional accounting challenges, such as data integration complexities across diverse sources and the need for standardization. The significance of these approaches is underscored by their dual benefit: not only do they enhance the timeliness of data management, but they also support more informed managerial decision-making. As emphasized in the article, *Methodological Aspects of the Digital Economy with a Focus on Statistical Forecasting Methods*, digital accounting methods mitigate risks associated with delays and inaccuracies inherent in traditional methods [1].

The findings of this study align with those of other researchers. For example, *Defining the Digital Economy for Statistical Research Purposes* highlights that traditional accounting methods often struggle with the vast volumes of data generated within the digital economy and stresses the need for more adaptable and modern solutions [2]. Furthermore, the Digital Economy and Society Index (DESI) shows that countries actively employing cloud and automated systems achieve higher levels of timeliness and accuracy in statistical accounting, consistent with our findings [4]. These results affirm that digitizing accounting processes has become not merely advantageous but essential for enhancing competitiveness.

One limitation of this study is the high cost of implementing digital technologies, which can be challenging for organizations with limited resources. Moreover, the processes of automation and data integration require skilled professionals, which can also impede widespread adoption. As noted in *Statistical Study of the Level of Digitalization in the Russian Economy: Problems and Prospects*, preparing specialists to work with big data and artificial intelligence remains a significant challenge due to the additional investment and time required [3]. These constraints may complicate the adaptation of traditional accounting methods to modern conditions, particularly for small and medium-sized enterprises.

To improve the quality of statistical accounting and the efficacy of managerial decisions, several areas warrant attention. Firstly, there is a need to develop training and education programs for data processing and analysis specialists to ensure organizations have access to a skilled workforce. Secondly, as resources allow, investment should be directed toward automation and cloud technologies, which help minimize errors and expedite accounting processes. DESI emphasizes that countries fostering digital infrastructure and incorporating modern approaches into accounting processes achieve higher levels of economic digitalization [4]. The implementation of digital technologies also enhances data transparency and facilitates better integration of information from diverse sources, a critical factor amid digital transformation.

Conclusion

The results of this study demonstrate that the adoption of digital technologies in statistical accounting is essential for enhancing accuracy, responsiveness, and efficiency in the context of a digital economy. Traditional data accounting methods struggle to meet modern demands due to the growing volume of information and the complexity of data integration. Automation, cloud technologies, and artificial intelligence methods have shown significant effectiveness in improving data quality and reducing human errors. Consequently, the implementation of modern approaches to statistical accounting not only enhances the quality of accounting practices but also bolsters organizations' competitiveness in the market [1].

For successful integration of digital technologies in statistical accounting, organizations and institutions should focus on the following areas:

1. **Investment in digital infrastructure:** Automation of accounting processes and the use of cloud technologies should be prioritized to improve data processing speed and quality.
2. **Specialist training:** Training employees and recruiting experts in data processing, artificial intelligence, and analytics will provide the foundation for the effective utilization of new technologies in accounting.
3. **Systematic data integration:** Implementing unified systems for data collection and storage will help improve the standardization and harmonization of information, reducing errors and increasing accounting reliability.

These recommendations can form the basis for modernizing statistical accounting within the digital economy, providing organizations with access to high-quality, accurate data to support decision-making.

Future research may focus on the development and testing of new technologies and tools to further enhance statistical accounting in the face of continuous digitalization. Promising directions include the creation of more flexible and resilient systems for integrating data from various sources, exploring ways to

improve data reliability through automated processing, and examining the impact of artificial intelligence on long-term accuracy and responsiveness in accounting. These studies will further drive the advancement of the digital economy and enable more informed decision-making at all levels of management [4].

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